

COMPARISON OF FETAL OUTCOME IN PATIENTS WITH VERSUS WITHOUT GESTATIONAL DIABETES MELLITUS IN TERMS OF MACROSOMIA

Dr. Sadia Abidi Malik¹, Lt. Col. Dr. Shaista Ambreen²

¹Post Graduate Trainee (FCPS Gynecology & Obstetrics), Combined Military Hospital, Sialkot.

²Assistant Professor / Classified Gynecologist, Gynecology & Obstetrics Department (Study Supervisor), Combined Military Hospital, Sialkot.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17129922>

Keywords

Gestational Diabetes, Macrosomia, Pregnancy Outcome, Fetal Growth, Cesarean Section, Neonatal Birth Weight.

Article History

Received on 14 May 2025

Accepted on 23 May 2025

Published on 28 May 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Sadia Abidi Malik

Abstract

Background: There is ongoing debate in the literature regarding the impact of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) on fetal macrosomia. To address this inconsistency, the present study was designed to compare fetal outcomes between women with and without GDM, with a particular focus on assessing the incidence and risk of macrosomia.

Objectives: To determine the association between gestational diabetes mellitus and macrosomia.

Duration: Six months w.e.f 01-08-2024 to 31-01-2025

Methodology: After ethical approval, 160 pregnant women meeting inclusion criteria at CMH Sialkot were enrolled with informed consent. They underwent a 75g oral glucose tolerance test to diagnose GDM. Based on results, 160 women were divided equally into GDM and non-GDM groups. All participants were followed until delivery and study outcomes were recorded. Deliveries were managed by the same senior consultant to minimize bias, and confounding variables were controlled through strict exclusion criteria. Data collection was performed by the resident to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Results: A total of 160 pregnant women (mean age 28.84 ± 4.75 years) were studied, with 64.4% overweight/obese. Cesarean section was more frequent in the GDM group (47.5%). Neonates of GDM mothers had higher birth weight and significantly greater macrosomia risk (28.7% vs. 13.8%, OR=2.53), consistent across age, BMI, parity, and gestational age subgroups.

Conclusion: In this study, gestational diabetes mellitus was associated with significantly higher neonatal birth weight and increased risk of macrosomia. Although differences in mode of delivery and subgroup analyses were not statistically significant, odds ratios consistently favored a higher risk in GDM cases, highlighting its impact on adverse fetal outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy imposes a significant metabolic burden, characterized by weight gain and progressive insulin resistance. In line with the global rise in obesity and metabolic disorders, gestational diabetes mellitus

(GDM) has become the most common medical complication of pregnancy.¹ According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), GDM affects around 14.0% of pregnancies worldwide,

accounting for approximately 20 million births annually.² In Pakistan, the reported prevalence of GDM is 17.7%.³

Women with GDM are at increased risk of developing gestational hypertension, pre-eclampsia, and often require delivery via cesarean section.² Additionally, GDM significantly impacts fetal health, leading to complications such as miscarriage, preterm delivery, congenital anomalies, hydroamnios, macrosomia, and unexplained fetal death.³ In cases of poorly controlled diabetes, maternal risks may extend to preeclampsia, diabetic ketoacidosis, nephropathy, retinopathy, and neuropathy.⁴

Among these complications, macrosomia is one of the most frequently observed outcomes of GDM, defined as a birth weight exceeding 4000 grams. This results from excessive fetal fat accumulation, particularly in the shoulders and trunk, increasing the risk of shoulder dystocia and cesarean delivery.⁵ Other neonatal outcomes like low Apgar scores, preterm birth, and neonatal death have been less consistently reported.⁶ To ensure timely diagnosis, universal screening for GDM is recommended between 24–28 weeks using a 75 g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT), as endorsed by IADPSG and adopted by WHO in 2013.⁷

Freitas et al. in Brazil reported a significantly higher frequency of macrosomia among infants born to women with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) compared to those without GDM (36.2% vs. 18.8%; $p = 0.00031$).⁸ Similarly, Groof et al. in Kuwait found higher macrosomia rates in GDM pregnancies (16.8% vs. 6.7%; $p = 0.001$).⁹ These findings support universal screening for GDM and close monitoring for macrosomia in affected pregnancies to enable better health planning and anticipate cesarean deliveries. However, in resource-limited settings like Pakistan, healthcare budgets require careful allocation. Contrarily, Kouhkan et al. in Iran reported no significant difference in macrosomia rates between GDM and non-GDM groups (5.68% vs. 2.67%; $p = 0.08$), highlighting ongoing controversy in the literature.¹⁰ Given the limited local and international data, this study aims to clarify the relationship between GDM and macrosomia. Confirming this link could improve patient management and reduce adverse outcomes, while

disproving it could help optimize healthcare resources.

METHODOLOGY

This cohort study was conducted in the Gynaecology and Obstetrics Department of Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Sialkot, over a period of six months following ethical approval. The study aimed to compare fetal outcomes, specifically macrosomia, in pregnant women with and without gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). A total sample size of 160 pregnant women (80 exposed to GDM and 80 non-exposed) was calculated to achieve 80% power and 5% significance, based on expected macrosomia frequencies of 36.20% in GDM and 18.80% in non-GDM groups, as reported by Freitas et al.⁸ Non-probability consecutive sampling was employed to select eligible participants aged 18 to 40 years, with gestational age ≥ 34 weeks confirmed by dating scans. Inclusion criteria encompassed women of any parity diagnosed with GDM according to a 75-gram oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT), where plasma glucose ≥ 153 mg/dl at two hours post-glucose load defined GDM, while healthy pregnant women without GDM formed the comparison group. Exclusion criteria included those with histories of steroid therapy, congenital fetal anomalies, significant cardiac, hepatic, or renal disease, and pregnancies complicated by oligohydramnios or polyhydramnios. After informed consent, 160 women attending routine outpatient checkups were screened; 160 fulfilling criteria were enrolled and divided into two groups: Group A (GDM, $n=80$) and Group B (non-GDM, $n=80$). Participants were followed until delivery, during which birth weight was recorded within 30 minutes on a calibrated digital scale, with macrosomia defined as birth weight ≥ 4000 grams. APGAR scores were also documented. To minimize bias, all deliveries were managed by the same senior consultant, and data collection was performed by a resident investigator. Potential confounders were controlled through stringent exclusion criteria. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Numerical variables such as age, BMI, parity, gestational age, and birth weight were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables like macrosomia were presented as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test compared macrosomia frequencies

between groups, with significance set at $p \leq 0.05$. Relative risk (RR) was calculated through 2x2 contingency tables, with $RR > 1$ indicating significant association. Stratification by age, BMI, parity, and gestational age was performed to identify effect modifiers, followed by post-stratification chi-square testing to determine statistical significance.

RESULTS

A total of 160 pregnant women were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 28.84 ± 4.75 years, with the majority (57.5%) falling in the 18-30 years age group, while 42.5% were between 31-40 years. The mean BMI was 26.68 ± 3.76 kg/m², with 35.6% of the women having a normal BMI and a greater proportion (64.4%) being classified as overweight or obese. The mean parity was 2.46 ± 1.07 , with 52.5% of the women having had 1-2 previous deliveries and 47.5% having had two or more. The mean gestational age at delivery was 37.51 ± 3.49 weeks, with 33.1% delivering between 34-36 weeks and 66.9% delivering at or beyond 37 weeks of gestation. Data is given in Table 1.0. At baseline both the groups were statistically comparable for all variables (p -value >0.05), as shown in Table 2.0. The mode of delivery showed a higher frequency of cesarean section in Group A (47.5%) compared to Group B (35.0%), though this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.108$). On the other hand, normal vaginal delivery was more common among non-

GDM women (65.0%) than among those with GDM (52.5%). The mean birth weight of neonates born to GDM mothers was significantly higher, measured at 3304.45 ± 571.41 grams, compared to 3113.18 ± 478.76 grams in the non-GDM group ($p = 0.023$). Furthermore, the incidence of macrosomia was significantly greater in Group A (28.7%) than in Group B (13.8%, $p = 0.020$). The calculated odds ratio (OR) for macrosomia in the GDM group was 2.532 (95% CI: 1.138-5.631), indicating that women with GDM were over two times more likely to deliver a macrosomic infant compared to those without GDM. Data is given in Table 3.0. The frequency of macrosomia was further stratified based on maternal age, BMI, parity, and gestational age at delivery. Across all subgroups, the occurrence of macrosomia was consistently higher in Group A (GDM) compared to Group B (non-GDM). However, these differences did not reach statistical significance, which may be attributed to the limited sample size within each subgroup. Despite the lack of statistical significance, the odds ratio (OR) for macrosomia in each subgroup remained consistently greater than 1, indicating a higher relative risk associated with GDM across all stratified variables. Data is given in Table 4.0.

Table 1.0: Demographic Characteristics of Patients Included in the Study

Characteristics	Total (160)
Age (years)	28.84 ± 4.75
• 18-30 years	92 (57.5%)
• 31-40 years	68 (42.5%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.68 ± 3.76
• Normal Weight	57 (35.6%)
• Overweight/Obese	103 (64.4%)
Parity	2.46 ± 1.07
• 1-2	84 (52.5%)
• ≥ 2	76 (47.5%)
Gestational Age at Delivery (weeks)	37.51 ± 3.49
• 34-36 weeks	53 (33.1%)
• ≥ 37 weeks	107 (66.9%)

Table 2.0: Comparison of Baseline Characteristics between the Study Groups

Characteristics	Group A (n=80)	Group B (n=80)	p-value
Age (years)	28.76±4.63	28.91±4.89	0.842
• 18-30 years	48 (60.0%)	44 (55.0%)	0.522
• 31-40 years	32 (40.0%)	36 (45.0%)	
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.77±3.68	26.59±3.86	0.763
• Normal Weight	32 (64.0%)	35 (70.0%)	
• Overweight/Obese	18 (36.0%)	15 (30.0%)	
Parity	2.45±1.05	2.48±1.10	0.884
• 1-2	26 (32.5%)	31 (38.8%)	0.409
• ≥2	54 (67.5%)	49 (61.3%)	
Gestational Age at Delivery (weeks)	37.46±2.16	37.55±4.46	0.875
• 34-36 weeks	28 (35.0%)	25 (31.3%)	0.614
• ≥37 weeks	52 (65.0%)	55 (68.8%)	

Chi Square test/ Independent sample t test, taking p-value≤0.05 as significant.

Table 3.0: Comparison of Study Outcomes between the Groups

Characteristics	Group A (n=80)	Group B (n=80)	p-value
Mode of Delivery			
• Cesarean Section	38 (47.5%)	28 (35.0%)	0.108
• Normal Vaginal Delivery	42 (52.5%)	52 (65.0%)	
Mean Birth Weight of the Baby	3304.45±571.41	3113.18±478.76	0.023
Macrosomia			
• Yes	23 (28.7%)	11 (13.8%)	0.020
• No	57 (71.3%)	69 (86.3%)	
ORR 2.532 (1.138-5.631)			

Chi Square test/ Independent sample t test, taking p-value≤0.05 as significant.

ORR >1 was considered as significant

Table 4.0: Frequency of Macrosomia Stratified on the basis of sub groups

Group	Sub Group	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value	ORR
Age	18-30 years	14 (29.2%)	6 (13.6%)	0.071	2.608
	31-40 years	9 (28.1%)	5 (13.9%)	0.147	2.426
BMI	Normal Weight	6 (23.1%)	3 (9.7%)	0.167	2.800
	Overweight/Obese	17 (31.5%)	8 (16.3%)	0.107	2.355
Parity	1-2	13 (29.5%)	5 (12.5%)	0.057	2.935
	≥2	10 (27.8%)	6 (15.0%)	0.172	2.531
Gest. Age at Delivery	34-36 weeks	11 (39.3%)	1 (4.0%)	0.002	15.529
	≥37 weeks	12 (23.1%)	10 (18.2%)	0.531	1.159

Chi Square test, taking $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$ as significant.

DISCUSSION

GDM is widely recognized as a risk factor for adverse fetal outcomes, particularly macrosomia. However, findings in the existing literature regarding the extent of this association remain inconsistent, with some studies reporting significant risks while others show minimal impact.¹¹⁻¹³ This controversy highlights the need for further investigation to clarify the relationship between GDM and fetal macrosomia.⁸⁻¹⁰ Therefore, this study was designed to compare fetal outcomes, specifically the incidence of macrosomia, between pregnant women with and without GDM. Our findings aim to provide clearer evidence to guide clinical management and improve perinatal care.

In this study, a total of 160 pregnant women were included, with a mean age of 28.84 ± 4.75 years and mean BMI of 26.68 ± 3.76 kg/m². Cesarean section was more common in the GDM group (47.5% vs. 35.0%, $p=0.108$). Mean birth weight was significantly higher in GDM cases (3304.45 ± 571.41 g vs. 3113.18 ± 478.76 g, $p=0.023$). Macrosomia occurred in 28.7% of GDM cases vs. 13.8% non-GDM ($p=0.020$, OR=2.532; 95% CI: 1.138-5.631).

While comparing our findings with existing literature, it is worth noting that Freitas et al. in Brazil also reported a significantly higher mean birth weight among infants born to mothers with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) ($p = 0.01$), along with a 4.7 times greater risk of macrosomia ($p = 0.001$), which aligns with our findings. In our study, neonates born to GDM mothers had a significantly higher mean birth weight, and the incidence of macrosomia was also significantly elevated, with an odds ratio of 2.532. However, unlike our observations regarding delivery mode trends, Freitas et al. did not find significant differences in maternal weight gain, height, history of GDM, or route of delivery between groups.⁸

Groof et al. in Kuwait similarly demonstrated a positive association between GDM and cesarean section (aOR = 1.76, 95% CI: 1.17-2.66), as well as fetal macrosomia (aOR = 2.36, 95% CI: 1.14-4.89). While our study did not find a statistically significant difference in cesarean rates between GDM and non-GDM groups ($p = 0.108$), a higher frequency of

cesarean delivery was noted in the GDM group, supporting a similar trend.⁹

Further corroborating these findings, Koukhan et al. in Iran reported significantly increased odds of adverse pregnancy outcomes maternal (OR = 2.43), intrapartum (OR = 2.05), perinatal (OR = 2.00), and neonatal (OR = 1.68) in women diagnosed with GDM. They concluded that these adverse outcomes were significantly correlated with GDM itself, rather than underlying risk factors, and emphasized the importance of early screening and management, especially in Asian and low-to-middle income populations.¹⁰

In Pakistan, Ejaz et al. found that neonates of GDM mothers had a higher mean birth weight compared to those of non-GDM mothers, a finding directly supported by our results.¹⁴ Akinyemi et al. in the USA identified GDM as an independent predictor of adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes, including cesarean delivery (OR = 1.40), maternal transfusion, ICU admission, neonatal intensive care admission (OR = 1.53), assisted ventilation (OR = 1.37), and low Apgar scores. These findings underscore the broad systemic impact of GDM, extending beyond just birth weight and macrosomia.⁷

Ifunanya et al. in Nigeria also reported significantly higher cesarean delivery rates among diabetic mothers (OR=9.6, 95% CI: 5.35-17.32, $p<0.0001$), and a higher incidence of polyhydramnios (OR=2.2, $p=0.02$). Their study found increased rates of macrosomia, neonatal hypoglycemia, and respiratory distress among infants born to diabetic mothers trends consistent with the complications associated with GDM noted in our study.¹⁵

Finally, Kumar et al. in India concluded that early screening for GDM in high-risk women is essential for improving maternal and neonatal outcomes, advocating that women diagnosed with GDM deliver in equipped healthcare facilities to manage complications effectively. This recommendation aligns with the implications of our findings, which highlight the elevated risk of macrosomia and the trend toward increased cesarean deliveries in GDM pregnancies.¹⁶

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that gestational diabetes mellitus is significantly associated with increased mean birth weight and a higher incidence of macrosomia. While cesarean section rates and subgroup analyses did not reach statistical significance, the consistently elevated odds ratios indicate an increased risk of macrosomia in women with GDM, highlighting the importance of monitoring and managing GDM to improve fetal outcomes.

LIMITATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

A key strength of this study is its comparative design, which allowed direct assessment of fetal outcomes in GDM versus non-GDM pregnancies. However, limitations include a relatively small sample size and single-center setting, which may affect generalizability. Additionally, potential confounders like glycemic control and maternal weight gain were not assessed. Future studies with larger, multicenter cohorts and more comprehensive data collection are recommended to further explore long-term neonatal outcomes and optimize GDM management strategies.

Conflict of Interest: None

Source of Funding: None

Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

Author 2

Substantial contributions to concept, study design

Data Analysis, Manuscript writing, Critical Review

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or

integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

REFERENCES

- Moon JH, Jang HC. Gestational diabetes mellitus: diagnostic approaches and maternal-offspring complications. *Diabetes Metab J*. 2022;46(1):3-14.
- Modzelewski R, Stefanowicz-Rutkowska MM, Matuszewski W, Bandurska-Stankiewicz EM. Gestational diabetes mellitus-recent literature review. *J Clin Med*. 2022;11(19):5736-45.
- Wali AS, Rafique R, Iftikhar S, Ambreen R, Yakoob MY. High proportion of overt diabetes mellitus in pregnancy and missed opportunity for early detection of diabetes at a tertiary care centre in Pakistan. *Pak J Med Sci*. 2020;36(1):38-43.
- Fatema K, Sultana N, Noor F. Characteristics of pre-gestational and gestational diabetes: a comparison of maternal and fetal outcome. *Sch Int J Obstet Gynec*. 2019; 2(12):319-26.
- Dogra A, Kumar V. Maternal and fetal outcome in patients with gestational diabetes mellitus. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2023;12(1):160-3.
- Dogra A, Kumar V. Maternal and fetal outcome in patients with gestational diabetes mellitus. Maternal and fetal outcome in patients with gestational diabetes mellitus. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2023;12(1):160-3.
- Akinyemi OA, Omokhodion OV, Fasokun ME, Makanjuola D, Ade-Ojo IP, Adeniyi AA. Screening for gestational diabetes mellitus: is there a need for early screening for all women in developing countries?. *Cureus*. 2023;15(2): e35533.
- Freitas IC, Hintz MC, Orth LC, Rosa TG, Iser BM, Psendziuk C. Comparison of maternal and fetal outcomes in parturients with and without a diagnosis of gestational diabetes. *Rev Bras Ginecol Obstet*. 2019;41(4):647-53.

- Groof Z, Garashi G, Husain H, Owayed S, AlBader S, Mouhsen H, et al. Prevalence, risk factors, and fetomaternal outcomes of gestational diabetes mellitus in Kuwait: a cross-sectional study. *J Diabetes Res.* 2019;5(1):1-7.
- Kouhkan A, Najafi L, Malek M, Baradaran HR, Hosseini R, Khajavi A, et al. Gestational diabetes mellitus: Major risk factors and pregnancy-related outcomes: a cohort study. *Int J Reprod BioMed.* 2021;19(9):827-36.
- Bernea EG, Uyy E, Mihai DA, Ceausu I, Ionescu-Tirgoviste C, Suica VI, et al. New born macrosomia in gestational diabetes mellitus. *Exp Ther Med.* 2022;24(6):710-16.
- Bai W, Wang H, Fang R, Lin M, Qin Y, Han H, et al. Evaluating the effect of gestational diabetes mellitus on macrosomia based on the characteristics of oral glucose tolerance test. *Clin Chim Acta.* 2023;544:117362.
- Mou SS, Gillies C, Hu J, Danielli M, Al Wattar BH, Khunti K, et al. Association between HbA1c levels and fetal macrosomia and large for gestational age babies in women with gestational diabetes mellitus: a systematic review and meta-analysis of 17,711 Women. *J Clin Med.* 2023;12(11):3852.
- Ejaz Z, Khan AA, Ullah SS, Hayat MA, Maqbool MA, Baig AA. The effects of gestational diabetes on fetus: a surveillance study. *Cureus.* 2023;15(2):1-6.
- Ifunanya NJ, Idzuinya OB, Okwuchukwu OV, Chibuzor UD, Chukwu IC, Nobert OC, et al. Evaluation of pregnancy outcomes among women with pregnancies complicated by diabetes mellitus in Abakaliki, South-East, Nigeria. *J Diab Mellitus.* 2019;9(3):69-76.
- Kumar V, Dogra A. Maternal and fetal outcome in patients with gestational diabetes mellitus. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol.* 2023;12(1):160-3.

